

BRIDGING GAPS WITH CO-TEACHING: A PATH TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATION

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Abstract

The professionalism of a teacher is not only identified with knowledge related to the discipline. Over time, a great transformation has been seen in the relationship between national programmes and teaching action, leading to the figure of the inclusive teacher. This work emphasises the professionalism of the support teacher and the increasingly specific and professional skills that the current situation requires. Special attention is paid to an inclusive and effective teaching perspective such as co-teaching, based on mutual collaboration, interchange of roles, shared planning and action strategies between curricular teacher and support teacher. It becomes a valid support for the development of effective educational - didactic methods. In an inclusive perspective, co-presence highlights the role of the support teacher who performs the function not only of supporting the whole class but also of co-teaching with the curricular colleague.

Keywords: Inclusion, Co-Teaching, Special Pedagogy.

Introduction

Disability may or may not be a temporary condition. In the case of disability, one cannot use the term curability but simply intervention: intervention for the improvement of the person's life. It represents the obstacle that prevents the individual with a deficit from completing a particular activity, from conforming to his or her own expectations and those of the surrounding context. Handicap constitutes a permanent condition where, however, intervention is always possible not only at a medical level, linked to the presence of a health condition, but also at a social level taking into account the environmental context in which the person lives.

According to the French physician Jean Marc Gaspard Itard (1802), considered to be the father of special pedagogy, it is "noted that the transition between normality and abnormality is not a nuance and that by dwelling on diversity one can discover the limits of normality itself, reversing the perspective and the angle from which one observes phenomena and events". Thus, the perspectives with which one observes are those obstacles and barriers of the social context that define the conditions of disability that lead to processes of marginalisation or

exclusion. The great complexity of the disabled person must be taken into account in order to arrive at important issues such as integration, inclusion, integration of the disabled person into the environment, care of the disabled person; thus, considering the disabled person as a full citizen. It is clear and fundamental, given the complexity of the disabled person, to dwell deeply on the issue of his or her inclusion, starting with the family and the school, which, as the main educational agencies, must learn to look beyond the condition of disability and have the objective of developing, in the disabled person, skills and good abilities, in order to ensure the full development of the autonomy possible. Thus, inclusion is a complex process that requires action from all those who, even with different roles, share an educational responsibility in a specific environment. The inclusive perspective in the school context can be realised with the careful, joint and coordinated action of the various professional figures to ensure a learning context designed for all, welcoming and offering specific and special responses also to pupils in difficulty and with disabilities without creating situations of welfarism or isolation and this is why the concept of co-presence is introduced (Ianes, 2016).

The possibility to activate a co-presence team is undoubtedly an important added value of today's educational experience. Having a colleague in the classroom is an opportunity to experiment, to provide a different perspective and to make pupils understand the importance of working together in synergy and collaboration by interweaving knowledge and skills. It is possible to design together from an inclusive perspective, and when you manage to personalise teaching, respecting the value of the diversity of a class group, the results are positive and have a great impact on all pupils.

This is why joint planning and collaboration between the support teacher and the curricular teacher becomes essential so that the pupils can rely on both and perceive them as reference figures on the same level. Co-teaching represents innovative and motivating teaching that is expressed through simple language that is close to the students, allows for long-lasting results and ensures better acquisition of basic skills. Embracing the idea of a school that believes in educational renewal by experimenting with a new methodology means questioning the traditional role of the teacher and renewing oneself by not being afraid of change, even radical change. In this regard, reference is made to a work by Edgar in which he states that: “there is never a prior consensus for innovation and one does not move forward from an average opinion, which is not democratic, but mediocratic. One moves forward from a creative passion. Today, transformative innovation is at the beginning of deviance. Deviance spreads to become a trend and then a historical force. We need a Pedagogical Revolution equivalent to that of the modern university, born in Berlin at the beginning of the 19th century. It is this university, today globalised, that must be revolutionised, retaining its experiences, but introducing the complex knowledge of our fundamental problems. It is the entire contemporary education system, based on the disciplinary model of the university and the disjunction between science and humanistic culture, that needs to be revolutionised in the same sense” (Morin, 2015).

Therefore, with respect to what has been said, it is necessary to speak concretely about copresence, understood as an innovative and renewing teaching methodology. Thus, co-presence can be used flexibly according to methodological choices and always involves careful, thoughtout planning, oriented towards sharing and understanding. It provides children with peace of mind, a desire to participate, and the opportunity to develop social and collaborative skills, which is just one of the goals of co-presence. It is a teaching style that favours the development of the whole person. Therefore, with respect to what has been stated, it emerges that in the school system the function of the support teacher is not separate from that of the class teacher, because it is of real support in the assumption of inclusive strategies and didactics directed at individualised interventions, centred on the characteristics and resources of the pupils in difficulty, and the pupils do not have to make any distinction when addressing the two teachers.

1. The support teacher between training and inclusive attitudes

Several studies (D'Alonzo,2018), (Lovecchio; Borgogni, 2022) have analysed the role of Pedagogy and Special Education in the evolution of the inclusive professional competences of the specialised support teacher by delving into the issue of the inclusive attitudes of these teachers who fully recognise the infinite variety of human differences and who should not be separated or distinguished from the curricular teachers. From an international perspective, the attitudes of teachers in inclusive school systems have been the subject of studies as they are the predominant element for the realisation of an inclusive learning environment. Inclusive attitudes act as mediators in the relationships between the values and action strategies of each teacher and are a fundamental element in the formation of a truly inclusive and united teaching staff. These studies show that many curricular teachers, before taking the specialisation course, perhaps thinking that their way of acting was guided by common sense, after acquiring a more adequate preparation realise that with their new knowledge they have a better chance of being inclusive teachers. Thus, we can confirm that “the value of the positive contamination that results from training, located yes in the area of support for pupils with disabilities but opening up to broader interpretations of the concept of inclusion, is recognised by teachers as a further possibility of becoming agents of change” (Caldin, 2009).

Dario Ianes (2016) argues that "the figure of the support teacher needs to be deconstructed, analysed and rethought from an inclusive perspective, offering the possibility of a reflection that allows for a broader reconsideration of the role of the teacher in general, reducing distinctions (curricular/support) and broadening connections, in order to arrive at a new conception of the inclusive teacher". This figure responds to the task of education and teaching by knowing how to recognise and value each person's differences while respecting their uniqueness. Therefore, the concept of inclusion must be taken from a social justice perspective, a perspective that underpins the construction of an inclusive society. The goal of building an inclusive society, however, must start with the construction of an inclusive school whose guiding principles need to be rooted in the fight against discrimination

and inequality and be aimed at removing barriers that hinder the learning and participation of all pupils in school life.

It follows that in an inclusive school, pupils' difficulties do not only concern their psychophysical characteristics, but affect all the obstacles to learning and participation that each pupil encounters in his or her educational pathway. In a context of inclusive schools and classrooms where the school population is increasingly diverse, teachers play a fundamental and decisive role in reaching the increasingly individualised needs and requirements of pupils.

Indeed, they are responsible for creating an inclusive climate and inclusive teaching in the classroom and the image of an inclusive society that they imprint on the minds of children and young people. Schools, inevitably, find themselves immersed and involved in the lives of children and adolescents, and our society, complex as it is today, requires us to fly high and constantly reminds us that we need to be there for the weakest, for the poor, for pupils with disabilities. Therefore, it is necessary to move towards a culture of solidarity that speaks of the need for the school as a privileged place of learning for the pupil with disabilities and of adequate training for those whose task it is to support those who alone can never make it. The school has the task of providing adequate support so that each person develops a conscious and free identity (Nuzzaci, 2022). Therefore, it is necessary for teachers to be adequately prepared in the field of inclusion so that they are ready to accept the challenge of change and turn their gaze towards the horizon of inclusion, no longer belonging to a specific role such as curricular or support, but becoming: "Teacher of All". Teachers, or rather inclusive teachers, are called upon to respond to profound needs and requirements that are the basis for future generations and change in each individual person. It is no longer as important how much and how I teach, but how much and how the learner learns. Hence the need for a figure who acts as an integrator and transforms the school into a community that wants to welcome and support everyone without fictions and pretences. Inevitably, there is a need for teaching that presents content in a way that is not one-sided but from different perspectives and that promotes altruism.

A figure who brings the class closer to the disabled fellow student, who brings everyone to the social good, and who represents the school community in producing learning directed at getting the other person's point of view (Piazza, 2009). In this chapter we will analyse the inner aspects that agitate the support teacher, the one who promotes a positive perception of the disabled pupil in others and who is the instrument capable of helping to transform the vision of the disabled person from an obstacle to a resource for the whole class, including fellow teachers.

The support teacher is often considered by curricular teachers as the expert trained to deal with students with disabilities, which is why, more often than not, curricular teachers convince themselves that they have no need and especially no duty to conduct any training on the subject.

Therefore, the support teacher in school is not a different teacher, but a particular teacher who has a specialisation that qualifies his or her professionalism and competence. His or her training is not to be understood as a sort of

"addition" to general training, but must be part of a precise and structured perspective that sees the specificity of a role that is always internal to teaching, albeit with particular characteristics and specific skills. The mission of today's teacher must conform to a highly democratic vision where respect for minorities and not the will of the majority prevails. One must have a desire to respect and care for those who need to be helped to be equals, to fulfil the need to be included in social life activities as the teacher of pedagogy, D'Alonzo (2018) states that if it is a person, it is right to offer the opportunity to live with others.

It all starts with the courage to stand by the disabled person and act as a shield. Care does not only mean assistance, but the growth and emancipation of the subject with disabilities in sustainable and reassuring environments capable of creating, through suitable means, the experiences that the subject faces on a daily basis and that can develop his or her emotional biography and thus a stable structure; these are behaviours in which the disabled person sees his or her own story connected to that of others. Through this educational action called 'care', a conscious, intentional change is built in the person, which leads to expanding not only the knowledge already possessed, but also the way of observing and constructing reality, transforming one's way of being. Any intentional change forces us to become aware not only of our starting knowledge, but also how, as we learn, we change and transform (Colella & Vasciarelli, 2020). Fundamental in this context is talking about the concept of "network", which introduces a vision of the support teacher by qualifying him or her as a network operator: that is, it opens up this role to a more extensive work within the school and outside, in the territory.

The network mentality leads the support teacher to think about the problems of the weak user no longer in 'essentialist' terms focused only around the disabled pupil, but rather in relational terms and thus relating to the network of relationships within which all the people involved in the problem move. Networking is part of a community care perspective, i.e. in a context of locality and social territoriality of which the school is only one, albeit important, element. But it is clear that the network, although horizontal and continuous, is focused by the support teacher within the school and the classroom. Therefore, the support teacher can develop those characteristics of the school community marked by solidarity, friendship, making it a true community of relationships that give a sense of belonging, sociability and generosity between students. The presence of the support teacher, fortunately and with its limitations, is a fundamental resource to promote an inclusive school community that does not exclude or privilege, but includes, unites without making differences.

2. Co-presence for real inclusive teaching

School inclusion on the horizon of social inclusion by going beyond the constraints, barriers and difficulties, which one may inevitably encounter, it is possible to achieve learning, behavioural and inclusive goals within the school context. Co-presence is concretely realised in a collaborative dimension in which the concept of interdisciplinarity is introduced and how important the intertwining of methodologies is, which undoubtedly provides an enrichment for both the pupils in the class and the teachers, who enhance their professionalism. In this perspective, the simple simultaneous presence in the classroom, called co-presence, based on mutual

collaboration, interchange of roles, shared planning and action strategies between the curricular teacher and the support teacher, becomes a valid support for the development of effective educational - teaching methods. The aspects of co-presence in an inclusive perspective highlights the role of the support teacher who performs the function not only of supporting the whole class but also of co-teaching with the curricular colleague (Ianes, 2016). And not only that, a benefit goes to pupils with special educational needs, since the support teacher can in fact become to all intents and purposes the teacher on and for the whole class and not only of the individual pupil with difficulties, thus offering equal opportunities to all pupils and promoting true inclusive teaching full of meaningful learning experiences (Ianes,2015).

An “inclusive school” is much more than a school that achieves good integration of pupils with disabilities and fully values all differences, from disabilities to brilliance. It starts from a basis of equality by welcoming every pupil into the school of all, regardless of how they function. This is only the starting point, because the point of arrival is that of justice as fairness, which distributes resources according to the needs of each individual, which seeks to go beyond standardised teaching, the same for all pupils, by making a structural differentiation that makes everyone accessible to different ways of learning, different ways of teaching, different materials and paths. So, the inclusive school is made every day with big and small choices and lovingly and rationally corrects and supports different individual situations through a global and professional perspective. In this perspective, co-presence fits right in, and the term co-presence is not synonymous with collaboration but represents an activity in which teachers interact using a collaborative style by sharing objectives, responsibilities and decisions that are essential for co-presence teaching. The rigorous and scientifically based definition of didactic co-presence is: "a shared instructional design, teaching and assessment strategy whereby two or more teachers, a curricular teacher and a support teacher, work together to provide educational services, instructional proposals, including basic and specialised instruction, to a heterogeneous group of learners from an inclusive perspective and within a single physical space" (Pouw, et Al., 2014). In order to be able to maintain a good collaborative relationship, teachers must agree and express their own pedagogical-educational convictions and personal intolerances so that they can respect each other and not offend the sensitivities of others, which would then severely compromise the climate of the collaborative relationship.

Dario Ianes (2015) states that the collaborative relationship requires time to engage in dialogue and to establish mutual trust in order to expand one's repertoire of co-presence strategies, so that the support teacher does not wander aimlessly within the classroom and the curricular teacher takes over all planning, teaching and evaluation responsibilities. Therefore, it is not enough to be present in the classroom at the same time sharing the same space and time to speak of didactic co-presence; neither is the division of tasks between the teachers so that while one of the two teaches, the second performs more practical tasks and/or any type of activity that does not support the pupils and the teaching.

If the collaborative dimension is missing and the division of roles and responsibilities does not take place, co-presence is reduced to the curricular teacher managing the classroom teaching while the support teacher assists the disabled pupil. Involvement is required of both teachers that provides students with new teaching proposals and support during the learning process that takes place within the classroom. In addition, teachers from different subject areas jointly implement their subjects within the same lesson, in contrast to CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning), i.e. the teaching and learning of language content in an integrated manner in which the foreign language is the medium of disciplinary learning.

In the case of CLIL, the collaboration is operational between teachers who organise, together, the lesson with certain characterising aspects:

- Lesson planning, scheduling and implementation.
- Identification of learning objectives. - Choice of topics to be proposed
- Preparation of material to be used - Shared evaluation of the results achieved.

One of the elements that make the difference with regard to the possibility of achieving quality school inclusion is the creation of a sufficiently cohesive class group, and we as adult educators have the role of circulating a positive current in the relationships within the class group by working closely with the relational dynamics that are established and eliminating the competitive component. According to the specialised teacher and trainer of inclusive methodologies, therefore, the competitive climate creates tension, dissatisfaction, anxiety and is still present in our classrooms. But the most important supportive resource in a classroom is the positive climate. This rests on three basic principles: collaborating, valuing and trusting (Scarinci, et Al., 2022). The classroom is a dynamic learning community, in which everyone makes their own resources available and introduces their own difficulties. Resources, even the apparently less significant ones, are enhanced by using them in the work. Finally, it should be specified that the term co-presence should not be linked to the term inclusion: the term inclusion refers to a practice whereby all students, with or without difficulties, are part of the same class and, more broadly, of the same learning community. Co-presence, therefore, is only one of many ways of extending inclusion.

3. The characteristics of co-teaching

The concept of co-presence is constantly evolving due to the different educational needs that characterise school contexts and require an increasingly timely, effective and efficient response. Today's teaching profession is based on relationships and the need for close cooperation with colleagues, which is why two professionals, on average a curricular teacher and a support teacher, with equivalent preparation but in different areas of expertise, together provide educational services and differentiated instruction to groups of students, with disabilities and/or high intellectual potential, enabling them to meet their needs (Ianes, 2011). This is made possible in a common space and takes the form of a four-stage practice:

- Co-planning enables teachers to plan together, define mutual responsibilities, respective roles and share content during lesson management. The motivation driving this phase is above all dialogue, aimed at valuing and understanding the opinions of others. Codesign is based on the relationship between teachers and between students and teachers. Planning is essential and teachers who plan regularly expand and increase their repertoire of strategies. Work sharing helps because if they spent little time on planning everything would be reduced to an approach of one teaching, the other assisting and observing, and today the needs of students and their contexts have changed and are more demanding.

- Co-teaching that requires changing the teaching style and the environment in which one physically acts.

- Co-assessment representing the interaction between teachers within the various school contexts and aiming at the development of social and communication skills that are the subject of the learning and assessment process. This phase goes hand in hand with the teaching phase.

- Feedback representing the essential communication skill that gives other people information about their behaviour and actions for different purposes. In order to cooperate, it is therefore necessary to be able to provide objective information about observed behaviour and situations enacted by other people and to provide information about the impressions or feelings that certain situations provoke.

Furthermore, a teacher couple that chooses and decides to work together, in order to complete the cooperation, must agree to:

- Working together voluntarily: only teachers who decide with their own will, and not because they are forced to by any obligation, be it regulatory, administrative or by the school head, can bring constructive and fruitful results.

- Feeling equal: there is mutual respect because in a situation of equality, teachers freely exchange ideas and opinions of equal value.

- Wanting to achieve a common goal: very often the will to collaborate arises from a common agreement to achieve an educational objective.

- Sharing responsibility and results: collaboration inevitably implies sharing responsibility for both the tasks assigned and the decisions to be taken; everyone is responsible for the results of the collaborative effort.

- Interweaving one's skills: the interaction between different trainings allows professionals to learn from each other.

- Co-operating and interacting in a positive way: the co-operative process finds fulfilment in the interaction between the different relational skills of the teachers.

The elements considered so far, for good and real collaboration, indicate the essential characteristics of co-presence teaching and it should be emphasised that, despite different application studies, the use of co-presence is a valid method of instruction for learning support.

It is hoped that it will be increasingly applied so that through collaborative work between teachers and with shared co-planning, fundamental educational goals can be achieved. The entire school world, from headmasters to various teachers, should be clear about the advantages and benefits because achieving true “universal education” is not a utopia but an important project aimed at achieving better teaching situations, learning and social outcomes in all pupils and the imprint of the value of justice as fairness in all of us. Teaching co-presence has many facets and embraces many collaborative dimensions between people in the school system. The school itself is a living organism that is constantly changing just think of the turnover in precariousness of many teachers, especially support teachers. Moving towards an inclusive horizon is a constant goal and means above all activating a cycle of improvement, verification of outcomes, self-analysis, planning, redesign and so on. The co-presence leads us to think, consequently, of the emergence of a single figure, the inclusive teacher, who plays an important role because he or she can be the main actor that stimulates and accompanies the processes of self-assessment and self-improvement of inclusiveness. As we could see, inclusion concerns the whole school, so it is addressed to everyone and not only to support teachers.

Hence, every teacher can acquire the adjective “inclusive” and become the main engine of development for the entire school; if everyone were committed to working well in inclusion, we would reach a community that works well for everyone and brings inclusive strategies closer and more integrated with general ones, aiming at an educational vision that is so differentiated and plural as to be universal. It is a universal school (Vasciarelli, 2020). An inclusive teacher is faced with many different situations that often change for an infinite number of reasons, and the development of an increasingly inclusive school requires him to go beyond habit, the mental laziness of the usual phrase “we have always done it this way”, of habits and patterns that lead one not to see what could be changed, what needs to be done, doing it differently or using it differently. Each of us, more or less, has experienced discovering new and unused spaces in the school itself or inventing new ways of using the usual spaces for different, more open and more articulated activities. Two characteristics in particular are required of this type of teacher: courage and creativity. Courage and creativity are needed to innovate the activities of those who teach and represent an extraordinary wealth that opens up great opportunities for diversification in learning. Imagination, creativity, fantasy associated with a good dose of courage are a resource for a school that can include everyone. An important step in this direction is to implement, within the teaching and organisational autonomy of schools, “mixed chairs”: i.e. made up of support hours and hours of teaching the class, in their own discipline. In this way, the support function spreads to a higher number of teachers and does not crystallise only in support teachers; of course, the number of hours in relation to the number of teaching staff can be different and vary according to need in an evolved vision of the school's functional staff. This change of role, on an equal footing, would facilitate co-design and inclusive teaching and create a rich functional staff that could be used in various classes according to circumstances. The mixed chairs are a step forward in normalising teachers' competences by overcoming the processes of delegation and de-empowerment, thus entering an evolutionary and radical phase

that envisages the transformation of current support teachers into full-fledged curricular teachers by universalising teaching and educational interventions for all pupils.

The Italian school has within it many truly competent and trained support teachers who risk being locked into limited, traditional roles where they cannot express their skills for the benefit of anyone. Through mixed chairs, it is possible to create a different role, more challenging and not within everyone's reach, that provides methodological support and concrete help in implementing various forms of inclusive teaching. The school as a whole needs teachers who spread their skills to all actors in the system, thus leading the support teacher to no longer exist, but dissolving and evolving in two directions forming a single figure who would be the inclusive teacher par excellence (Ianes, 2016). Thus, school inclusion in Italy has gone through and experienced a long evolution that has seen the succession of different regulatory stages.

The discussion between laws and decrees that have made the way for the inclusion of pupils with disabilities has been wide-ranging and not all provisions have been an effective means of achieving the “inclusive” goals we all hope for, and it is rather complicated to get our hands on and comment on a complex set of regulations, but we will try. During this, not short, discussion, two structural fractures between school grades and the role of curricular and specialised support teachers were formed. The strong separation between pre-school and secondary school, moreover, represented a detrimental fracture that widened in the years to come; the separation of roles between teachers, on the other hand, fostered mechanisms of de-empowerment causing the phenomenon whereby curricular teachers 'delegate' the issue of integration to their support colleagues, thus giving rise to a negative participation and membership in the class group (Humburg,2020). Starting from law no. 104/92, which basically concerns assistance, social integration and the rights of disabled persons, a start was made on guaranteeing the right to schooling in ordinary classes for pupils medically assessed as “unschooled”, the right for disabled pupils to attend nursery and kindergarten, and the provision of suitable teaching strategies and financial means to ensure the implementation of these principles.

Law No. 104/92, however, has always presented in itself a statist and medical vision, lacking school autonomy and still viewing disability in a static and egocentric manner. In relation to the training of support and curricular teachers, it has always ignored the study and in-depth study of special pedagogy and inclusive teaching. It was only in 2010 that Ministerial Decree No. 249 introduced, for the university training of future teachers, a broader vision of special pedagogical elements and special didactics useful for guaranteeing a real take-over of the inclusive project by both teachers, support teachers but above all curricular teachers.

Conclusion

There are certainly benefits to be derived from the implementation of teaching coparticipation, first and foremost for students with difficulties or disabilities who, thanks to this methodology, feel and are above all welcomed in their needs, giving them a concrete response translated into support aimed at promoting their learning as well. Provided with adequate support and clear and diverse learning strategies, even students with Special Educational

Needs can achieve goals tailored to their possibilities. Thanks to the didactic co-presence, all students count on the support of a teacher who is an expert in educational content and a teacher who is an expert in educational strategies (Saleh, 2020). Moreover, teachers themselves can count on the collaborative support of another teacher or other teachers with whom they can share both the successes and problems of the class, thus decreasing the stress level, easing the emotional burden of teaching and also being more able to follow students in an individualised manner. Many studies have shown that co-presence has great potential for promoting inclusion regardless of the strategy used. Levels of involvement among teachers, students and other staff have increased and brought satisfactory results. In schools, many operators with different professional profiles, roles and training related to social realities work in the educational and care role, so we can argue that co-presence involves everyone a little bit. Certainly the most accessible form of didactic co-presence is that between two teachers, curricular and support, but there may also be other, unconventional forms of co-presence that are worth trying and that should be studied and disseminated; one should not be afraid to collaborate together, for the common good, with all the members of the school world and therefore consider in this great inclusive team: internal and external technical experts; parents and family members and finally the pupils around whom the collaboration of all these figures revolves (Caldin, 2009).

In the case of the experts/technicians, we are dealing with a large team made up of figures who possess a specific expertise that the teacher is not supposed to have and who deserve to be listed one by one: the sports coach, the policeman, the programmer, the librarian, the instructor, the ABA technician specialising in autism, the speech therapist, the pedagogue, the psychomotor therapist, the psychologist, the theatre director, the pet therapist, the cook, the art therapist and many others. The best use of these figures on a practical level is precisely in programming all activities, conducting them together with a clear map of actions on the basis of a methodological scheme. It is important that there is a clearly delineated pedagogical model of the co-presence and the actions to be followed. Obviously all in collaboration with the teachers' teaching practices.

In the case of parents and family members, it is very interesting and can bring unexpected resources into the school, such as: parents from other cultures and other languages can enrich the teaching situation by enhancing diversity or the real contributions of working parents who bring their experiences of everyday life. Here too, joint planning of activities and shared conduct is effective and if the activity is conducted on the basis of a clear methodological scheme, what brings a parent or family member into a teaching process will yield the best possible results. Therefore, a fully inclusive school is one in which dialogue, listening, confrontation, and the shared and collaborative search for solutions become widespread practices in the relationship between school and parents.

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